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Abstract

The fine-scale spatial patterns of forest understory vegetation have been analyzed, using information theory models developed by Juhász-Nagy, to compare 31 beech forest sites grouped into three categories ("coppice", "high forest", "old-growth"). The models of florula diversity and associatum describe the spatial variability of species combinations and spatial dependence of populations, two aspects of community composition, with an explicit reference to spatial scaling. The three categories showed different trends in the values of florula diversity, associatum, relative associatum and their respective characteristic areas, corresponding to the function maxima. Significant differences in the characteristic area of FD have been found between high forest and the other two categories, with similar results for the characteristic area of AS. Coppice sites showed lower FD. Old-growth sites showed significantly higher AS, high FD and higher characteristic areas of both functions than high forest. Complete spatial randomization and random shift null models have been applied to the field data: the results deviate from the CSR but not from the RS model, suggesting high intraspecific spatial autocorrelation. Leaf area index measurements were compared across categories, showing significantly higher values in coppice than in old-growth forest, with old-growth being lower than high forest as well. Overall, old-growth forest sites have been found to show high compositional diversity supported by complexity, larger characteristic areas and a less dense canopy. Younger regenerating stands showed the lowest diversity and least organized community, according to the combination of high FD, low AS and small characteristic areas.

Keywords: beech forest, understory, management, old-growth, coppicing, beta diversity, JNP models, florula diversity, associatum, LAI.

I. Introduction

The forest understory layer, despite representing a small proportion of the biomass, makes up the largest part of forest plant richness and diversity¹. The importance extends to ecosystem functions, including nutrient cycling and plant production², soil protection, buildup of soil nutrients³.

Understory affects overstory through regeneration of the tree species by seedlings⁴ and succession⁵. Herb layer species richness has been found to be correlated with stand properties like total N and site index (H_{100})⁶, the expected top height of the stand at a total age of 100 years⁷.

The effects of stand-level management^{8,9,10} and disturbance¹¹ on the understory plant diversity have been discussed multiple times. Forest understory is considered a good ecological and dynamic indicator, reflecting tree harvesting regimes¹², herbivory disturbance¹³, forest floor disturbance¹⁴. Overstory influences the environment of understory plants, in microclimate¹⁵ and resource availability¹⁶; light availability is one of the mechanisms through which the canopy structure affects understory species diversity¹⁷, with heterogeneity enhancing diversity, allowing the survival of light-demanding species¹⁸. Scale-dependent relationships have been highlighted between overstory age or tree density and understory richness and diversity¹⁹.

In particular, some studies have been focused on beech forests (*Fagus sylvatica* L.), with coppicing being the most common management strategy^{20,21}. Coppicing is a practice widespread in Europe, especially in the southern countries²². It relies on vegetative re-sprouting of felled trees, usually carried out with short rotation periods of 15-30 years^{20,21}. In the last decades, many coppiced stands in Italy have been abandoned²³ or converted to high forest management, through selective thinning, in a process that last many decades with the goal of a continuous cover of adult trees²⁴.

The results of studies measuring understory diversity across management and stand ages aren't univocal. In general, it has been observed a decrease of understory diversity with stand age in secondary succession²⁵, but contrasting results come from the study of coppicing, which found either a significant non-linear negative correlation of richness with age²⁶ or no significant relationship at plot scale, while one site showed lower total richness at the forest patch level²⁰.

Ecology has historically been concerned with the relationships between pattern and process, between spatial and temporal dynamics^{27,28,29}, so every analysis of a temporal process such as succession, or the trajectory of a system after human intervention, must consider the real topographic space⁵². It's then hypothesized that measures of fine-scale compositional diversity, rather than *simplex* diversity (namely, classic richness and taxon-abundance measures),

can be sensitive to management types. Most studies have looked at α diversity at stand scale³⁰, or β diversity at landscape scale^{31,32,20,33}. Studies that have measured β diversity or compositional turnover within-stand usually do so with elementary sampling units with a dimension of a few meters^{10,34}, while smaller scales are mostly unexplored in forests^{35,48}.

Old-growth forests show high vertical and horizontal structural complexity, resulting in fine-scale spatial heterogeneity, due to the creation of gaps and overall thinning of the overstory³⁶. It has been found that understory plants in old-growth forest have a patchy distribution, following the heterogeneous distribution of resources³⁷; the complexity of canopy structure puts constraints on the understory environment, resulting in less freedom of species combinations and stronger spatial dependence³⁸.

Environmental heterogeneity can increase biodiversity, as stated in the habitat heterogeneity hypothesis^{39,40}, but the sign of the relationship can change depending on scale, with negative relationships more common at small scales⁴¹; the amount of heterogeneity also entails trade-offs due to stochastic extinctions⁴².

Up to this point, the importance of scale in plant ecology, a central theme for the discipline^{43,44}, has been remarked multiple times. In particular, the importance of fine-scale processes has been emphasized⁴⁵. In the physical space, species occur as combinations, and the importance of fine-scale pattern and variability of these combinations has been shown to be important for the maintenance of biodiversity^{46,47,48}.

Putting together these requirements necessitates biodiversity measures that treat the multivariate patterns of species compositions and the spatial process explicitly at each scale. Pál Juhász-Nagy developed a framework of models^{49,50,51,52,53} based on information theory, collectively called “JNP models”, with plant ecology explicitly in mind. The models represent ecologically relevant features, like species coexistence and association³⁸.

The measures of Florula Diversity (FD) and Associatum (AS) have been applied the most in field studies, and are the focus of this case, too. Florula Diversity is an entropy estimate of species combinations; Associatum is the mutual information of species, a measure of multivariate specific association. Respectively, they describe two fundamental attributes of community structure: spatial variability and spatial dependence⁵⁴. All the measures are in terms of a specific scale, and are usually evaluated in multiple scaling steps.

Because of the explicit scale dependence of these measures, they will have different values at each scale. The maxima of the two measures, and the scale at which they are reached (characteristic areas), represent ecologically relevant features of the community, “coenostate descriptors”, and are usually plotted in an abstract “coenostate spaces”. The two complementary planes of AS/FD and their characteristic areas can give information about the pattern generating mechanisms and dynamic succession trajectories⁵⁴.

Some studies have already applied the JNP models to forest understory communities, in particular for monitoring³⁸, comparing regenerating and primary phytocoenoses⁵⁵, evaluating temporal dynamics of diversity with management³⁵ and in permanent plot studies⁴⁸. FD and AS have been found to follow unimodal relationships, with a single maximum somewhere between the elementary sampling scale and the largest sampling step, if the sampling is adequate.

The present study aims to compare, using compositional diversity and spatial dependence measures belonging to the JNP models, three categories of beech forest dynamic phases: old-growth, high forest and coppice.

Based on the results of previous studies^{38,35,55}, older stands are expected to show a lower FD maximum at a larger scale, compared with more recently disturbed stands in the coppice category; for AS, higher maxima in the least recently logged stands are expected, again at a larger characteristic scale. This reflects the constraints put on understory species combinations by the more complex canopy structure of old-growth forest³⁸. Conversely, high forest,

representing a more complete canopy closure and vertical homogeneity, is expected to show low values of both FD and AS and low characteristic scales compared with more recently disturbed and undisturbed stands, because of the decrease of species richness associated with canopy closure⁵⁶.

Because of the aforementioned impact of light availability on understory, availability and heterogeneity of this resource are considered to be an important factor differentiating the three categories taken into consideration. To measure those differences, Leaf Area Index (LAI)⁵⁷ is taken as measure of crown cover and within-stand variability.

The hypotheses can be thus summarized:

1. Florula diversity, Associatum. and relative AS vary between management categories (which reflect the time since the last human intervention and its kind). In particular, FD is lower in older stands because of the environment allowing less freedom for species combinations; AS is higher in older stands because of the stronger spatial dependence. Intermediate, even-aged stands will show low FD and low AS because of the more homogeneous canopy cover.
2. The values of FD, AS and relative AS are scale dependent with a single maximum value; the scale of the maxima is meaningful, and is higher for both measures in older stands than in more recently disturbed ones; intermediate ages show low characteristic scales.
3. Light is an important resource shaping the understory community; light availability and heterogeneity differ between management categories and are related to spatial community attributes, with higher values in the younger and older stands.

II. Methods

a. JNP models

1. Florula Diversity (FD)

Often, the basic unit of biodiversity studies is the individual, expressed as number of individual belonging to a taxon; if instead the unit is taken to be the combination of species in a sampling unit, a *florula*, biodiversity measures such as Shannon entropy can be used on the supraindividual unit, to evaluate compositional variability at different sampling scales. Florula Diversity⁵², alternatively called Floral Diversity⁴⁹, Biotic Diversity⁵³, Floral Entropy⁵¹ or Biotal Diversity⁵⁰, is an entropy estimate of the Shannon type of f_j , the frequency of species combinations according to a defined sampling scheme, realized as a 2^s contingency table (with s being the number of species). Florula diversity is a measure of spatial variability⁵⁴.

It is defined as:

$$m \hat{H}_j^{(\varphi)} = m \log m - \sum_{k=1}^{\omega} f_{kj} \log(f_{kj}) \quad (1)$$

With f_{kj} being the frequency of species combination k at a sampling scale j , m being the number of sampling units. A sampling scheme is defined in terms of shape, size, number and algorithm⁵⁸. Following custom, all these parameters are fixed except for size, so the subscript j , wherever found, indicates dependence on sampling scale. $\omega = 2^s$, the maximum number of possible species combinations.

2. Local Distinctiveness (LD)

Local distinctiveness⁵² is the pooled entropy estimate of local species behavior, that is, the uncertainty of finding a certain species in a random sampling unit, summed for all species present.

First let's define, for species i :

$$m\hat{H}_i = m \log m - n_i \log n_i - (m - n_i) \log (m - n_i) \quad (2)$$

The entropy estimate of species i , with m the number of sampling units and n_i the number of sampling units in which i is present. Thus, for all species:

$$m\hat{H}([L]) = s m \log m - \sum (n_i \log n_i + (m - n_i) \log (m - n_i)) \quad (3)$$

Local distinctiveness is a measure of the “individualistic behavior” of species, and is not considered here *per se*, but only to calculate associatum. The relation in (4) shows that AS, LD and FD are canonical, so two of them are sufficient to characterize a coenostate.

3. Associatum (AS)

Associatum⁵⁹ is the mutual information of s species, the contingency information of a 2^s table. In other words, it's the extension to the 2^s case of pairwise interspecific association. Associatum is a measure of spatial dependence⁵⁴. In the case of spatial independence, the expected uncertainty of species combinations is equal to the pooled entropy. If there is spatial dependence, information about one population will decrease the uncertainty about some others, and there will be a difference between the two entropy estimates. Thus, AS is calculated simply as:

$$m\hat{I}_j(\lambda) = m\hat{H}([L]) - m\hat{H}_j^{(\varphi)} \quad (4)$$

The three main quantities can be represented together in a Venn diagram as follows, with the sets making up the diagram being the local entropy estimates for populations A, B, ..., S (where their sum equals LD), the overall entropy bound being FD, and the intersection being AS:

Figure 1: Euler-Venn diagram relating the three main quantities FD, LD, AS in the case of $AS > 0$. Adapted from Juhász-Nagy (1984)⁵⁰.

4. Coenostate space

The maximum values of FD and AS, FD_{\max} and AS_{\max} , as well as the area of the sampling step j at which they occur, their “characteristic areas”⁵⁴ CA_{FD} and CA_{AS} , are representative of community pattern and dynamics and can be placed in an abstract “coenostate space”⁵⁴ of derived variables.

5. Relative associatum

Since the value of associatum depends on the diversity of a community³⁸, in particular being bounded by the value of FD, a standardized version called *relative associatum* might be more appropriate for comparisons.

Here, it is defined as:

$$AS_{rel(j)} = m \hat{I}_j(\lambda) / m \hat{H}_j^{(\varphi)} \quad (5)$$

Which is functionally equivalent to *simple relative associatum* in Juhász-Nagy (1984)⁵¹.

6. Randomizations

Spatial dependence can have multiple causes, such as intraspecific or interspecific competition, dispersal limitation or habitat heterogeneity. To disentangle these effects, two types of randomizations are executed on the data: complete spatial randomization (CSR) and random shifts (RS). CSR keeps the textural aspects of species richness and abundance by randomizing the position of each occurrence in the original data; RS keeps the intraspecific pattern as well as the textural elements, but randomly rotates and shifts each specific pattern relative to each other to remove interspecific association. 100 randomizations have been performed for each site for each of the two null models, with the functions of the JNP models evaluated at the same sampling scales as for the field data.

Since it can be derived that in an adequately sampled, completely random community of infinite spatial extension, $FD=LD$, $AS=0$ ⁵⁴, a non-zero value of AS in CSR can be attributed to causes other than preferential behavior of species, such as biases from a finite spatial extension. A measure is here introduced: being AS_r , residual associatum, the associatum of the random community, AS_{eff} , effective associatum, calculated as the difference between the AS of the real community and AS_r , represents a measure of association not explained by the null model. This measure is equivalent to *associatum difference* in the case of random shifts⁶⁰.

b. Study area and sampling

The study area is located in the Foreste Casentinesi National Park, across the border of the regions Toscana and Emilia-Romagna. This area features an

integral reserve zone, Sasso Fratino, instituted in 1959, which is the largest one of seven old-growth beech forests recognized in Italy by UNESCO⁶¹. Strict non-intervention management is required for this area. Not all of the forested area is thus protected, with zones that are still actively logged, others more recently abandoned; finally, some once logged stands are more actively managed for conversion to high forest, with selective cuts and harvesting of deadwood allowed.

31 sites were selected in which *Fagus sylvatica* was the dominant or only tree species, and delimited by a 30×30 m square plot. Based on the estimated last human intervention and protection status, the plots were subdivided in three categories (“Coppice”, “High forest”, “Old-growth”), with 9, 8, 14 plots each.

Sampling was carried out in July 2021 and July 2022, such that seasonal variations can be reduced. Interannual variations must be assumed to be negligible.

In each plot a circular transect, which is topologically a loop, was laid down, of length 100m, and contiguous sampling units of 10×10 cm considered along all its external perimeter. Transect sampling, while more time-efficient, has been found to be adequate for estimating information statistical functions⁶². This choice of resolution and extent was found to be adequate and necessary in previous studies^{38,48}.

Figure 2: Location of sites within the Foreste Casentinesi National Park. Green = old-growth, red = coppice, yellow = high forest. Mean coordinates 43.827° N 11.845° E ©OpenStreetMap

As it is usual for the evaluation of JNP models, field data has been converted to a binary outcome based on the intersection of the elements of a plant population set with the sampling units; the resulting matrix data is often improperly called “presence/absence”⁵¹. For this purpose, all vascular plants with height <1.30 m (“breast height”), with any organ intersecting the sampling unit (rooting and covering) have been considered.

The data thus collected has then been used in an example of space series analysis⁶³ with successive computerized resampling: in particular complete sampling, which means from all possible overlapping sampling units⁶⁴, while keeping the number of sampling units (n=1000) the same for each step. The step sizes were chosen according to a geometric progression.

Rare species have been found to bias information theory function, especially in the case of AS, without affecting the location of the peaks due to dominant species⁶⁵. Following Szollát & Bartha (1991)⁶⁶, species with a frequency below 3% have been removed from transect data.

c. Leaf Area Index

To calculate the LAI, for each site 12 camera pictures of the dominant crown layer have been taken, following a systematic 3×4 grid, with points spaced 7-20 m, depending on the density and heterogeneity of the site. The images have been captured with a Nikon D90 digital camera equipped with a 50mm Nikkor fixed lens. The camera has been placed at a height of 1.30 m and pointed to the zenith. The images have been acquired in raw format (NEF) and then converted to grayscale, with enhancement of the blue channel. The images have then been used to calculate the Leaf Area Index, according to the protocol in Chianucci (2020)⁶⁷. While the mean LAI value for each site is used as measure of canopy closure, the percent coefficient of variation ($CV_{LAI} \%$) can give information about within-site heterogeneity, albeit at a coarser scale than for the coenological study.

d. Statistical analysis

To find significant differences in the maxima of FD, AS, AS_{rel} and their respective characteristic areas between the three categories, the distributions were first tested for normality with the Shapiro-Wilk test. Since only some of the data resulted to be normally distributed, and the number of replicates in each category was low in any case, the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test was used to find differences between the categories. In the case of a significant result, the pairwise Wilcoxon rank sum test was done to find which categories differed and the significance level, with the Benjamini & Hochberg correction.

Distributions of LAI and $CV_{LAI} \%$ were found to be normal, according to the Shapiro-Wilk test, so homogeneity of variance was tested with Levene's test before performing ANOVA. Outliers were checked with box plot methods. To identify significant pairwise differences, Tukey's honest significant difference test was performed *post hoc*.

e. Software

All data was managed and calculations brought out in the R environment⁶⁸. JNP models analysis was done with the `comspat` package⁶⁹. Plots were made with the package `ggplot2`⁷⁰. The statistical tests are included in the package `rstatix`⁷¹.

III. Results

a. Information theory functions by site

Firstly, plotting the values of FD and AS at different scales shows values that mostly agree with the unimodal expectation, with peaks at a scale between that of the elementary sampling unit and that of the whole transect, both for the individual sites and for the average of each category.

One coppice site, T22, showed a second peak in FD and values of both functions at large scales distinctly different from the others in the category. Since these are attained at scales which are comparable with those of the transect, care must be taken before drawing any conclusion about this, because edge effects can become important⁶⁹.

Given the large number of sites, displaying the average of each category and the standard error at each secondary sampling scale resulted in the most orderly and comprehensible representation. For FD, inferences can be made about the significantly different values at small scales, with the relationship HF(high forest) > OG(old-growth) > C(coppice). High forest plots on average reach the maximum values of FD at smaller areas, and at large areas the value of OG and C is significantly higher than for HF.

For AS, the average value for C at small scales is slightly lower than for the other two categories, but otherwise C and OG reach significantly higher values at large scales, and their absolute maxima are higher too. Care must be taken in interpreting the apparently higher scale of maximum AS for coppice in this specific plot, because of the effect of the outlier coppice site.

Figure 3: average values of FD in bits and standard error at each secondary sampling scale, for each category.

Figure 4: average values of AS in bits and standard error at each secondary sampling scale, for each category.

Relative AS shows no significant differences at any scale, except for the slightly higher maximum value and scale for C, again imputable to the outlier. This result implies that the observed differences in AS cannot be disentangled from the influence of FD in this particular study.

Figure 5: average values of relative AS in bits and standard error at each secondary sampling scale, for each category.

Effective associatum, with residual associatum calculated from the average of CSR, shows for most sites a negative peak at small sampling scales and a positive peak at large scales. While associatum is expected to give positive values both in the case of positive and negative associations, negative values are possible for effective associatum⁶⁰. Nevertheless, the negative peak has a larger absolute AS_{eff} for C and OG than for HF, while AS_{eff} is higher for OG than for C at the peak area $> 1 \text{ m}^2$.

Figure 6: average values of effective AS in bits and standard error at each secondary sampling scale, for each category. Residual AS calculated from the CSR null model.

b. Coenostate space representation

Plotting the maximum values of FD and AS, and their characteristic areas, in the abstract coenostate space more clearly shows the distinctions of the peaks between the sites. The highest values of both AS and FD are reached in old-growth forest sites, but a number of them peaks at low values; coppices reach intermediate values of FD, but lower AS; high forest shows lower AS too, with FD being either high or low.

The representation by characteristic areas shows that most high forest sites reach their information model maxima at smaller scales than coppice and old-growth, while there's no clear distinction between the latter.

Figure 7: state-space representation based on the maximum values of FD and AS, divided by category.

Figure 8: state-space representation based on the sampling area at which the maxima of FD and AS are reached, divided by category.

c. Comparisons between categories

Further analysis has been done on FD, AS and AS_{rel} . Before proceeding to the graphical and statistical comparison of the values of the information theory functions maxima by category, the data can be summarized in a table:

Category	FD	CA_{FD}	AS	CA_{AS}	AS_{rel}	CA_{ASrel}
Coppice	4.146	0.580	1.521	1.020	0.400	1.020
	4.404	0.580 A**	2.242	1.020	0.568	1.810
	4.679	0.770	2.348	1.360	0.789	1.810
High forest	4.315	0.090	0.684	0.283	0.159	0.580
	5.236	0.215 B	1.408	0.580	0.464	1.020
	5.641	0.330	2.582	0.918	0.601	1.360
Old-growth	4.332	0.330	0.729	0.770	0.234	0.770
	5.121	0.380 A*	2.881	1.020	0.594	1.190
	5.772	0.580	4.017	1.698	0.911	1.810

Table 1: first quartile, median and third quartile of the maximum values of each function for a site, grouped by category. Letters indicate significant differences according to the Kruskal-Wallis test (* = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.005$, Benjamini & Hochberg adjusted post-hoc test).

Showing the maxima of the functions in a box plot by categories gives a more clear representation for comparative purposes. For FD, the median in coppice sites is lower than in the other two categories.

Figure 9: box plot of maximum FD values for each site, grouped by category.

For AS, the higher values in old-growth are evident once again, while high forest shows to be lower than both coppice and old-growth. The differences become less clear once AS is normalized by FD.

Figure 10: box plot of maximum AS values for each site, grouped by category.

Figure 11: box plot of maximum relative AS values for each site, grouped by category.

The same representation can be used for the characteristic areas of FD and AS. In both cases, it is confirmed that the median characteristic areas for high forest are lower than for the other two categories; coppices seem to have

significantly higher CA_{FD} , followed by old-growth, but the first category shows outliers in both plots, suggesting it is not as homogeneous as assumed.

Figure 12: box plot of the area of maximum FD for each site, grouped by category. Letters indicate significant differences according to the Kruskal-Wallis test (* = $p < 0.05$, ** = $p < 0.005$, Benjamini & Hochberg adjusted post-hoc test).

The characteristic area of AS shows the same relationships, with both coppice and old-growth reaching the maxima at higher scales than high forest.

Figure 13: box plot of the area of maximum AS for each site, grouped by category.

Relative associatum confirms a larger characteristic area for coppice than for high forest.

Figure 14: box plot of the area of maximum relative AS for each site, grouped by category.

d. Randomizations

Comparing the average values of the functions for each category and the standard error against the results obtained from the CSR and RS null models can illustrate the possible assembly mechanisms behind the observed patterns.

Figure 15: average value and standard error of FD in each category; field data compared against the mean result of 100 randomization of each type for each site.

Figure 16: average value and standard error of AS in each category; field data compared against the mean result of 100 randomization of each type for each site.

For all three categories and both FD and AS, the curves evidently differ from the CSR null model, but not from the RS model. This suggests that the observed patterns are not random, but are driven by intraspecific spatial autocorrelations.

In particular, for FD the differences hold for large scales, while at scales less than the characteristic areas, the field values do not deviate from both null models, such that the observed FD at these scales is driven mostly by species richness and abundance.

The area of maximum AS being higher for field data than for the CSR model, once again suggests a non-random, clumped pattern.

e. Leaf Area Index

To evaluate whether the observed differences can be attributed to differences in crown cover density and light intercepted by the tree canopy, the average of the LAI measurements has been compared between categories; the percent coefficient of variation (CV %) has been taken as variable representing the canopy heterogeneity within site, and compared the same way between categories.

Figure 17: box plot of the mean LAI for each site, grouped by category. Significant differences between categories according to one-way ANOVA and Tukey HSD post-hoc tests (* = $p < 0.05$).

Figure 18: box plot of the CV % of LAI for each site, grouped by category.

Significant differences have been found in the LAI between the coppice and the old-growth category. The coppice category includes two extreme outliers, but the results of the statistical tests didn't change whether they were included or not. The median LAI for old-growth is in any case lower than for high forest as well. The CV_{LAI} % of high forest is lower than for coppice and old-

growth, so it can be said that the crown cover in sites belonging to this category is more homogeneous than for the other two.

IV. Discussion

The classic JNP models measures of FD and AS highlighted differences in the understory community composition (properly intended as arrangement of elements in a space), heterogeneity and spatial dependence, which are often still evident after the performed grouping by categories. Although not rigorously defined by stand age, the categories used represent three distinct management and protection strategies and different stages of a trajectory of recovery from logging. The results reported for old-growth forests, compared with more recently disturbed stands, of higher AS conform to previous studies^{38,55}, in that most of the highest maximum values were found in this category, although there is considerable variability within it. The consistently high characteristic areas for both FD and AS are likewise in agreement. An unexpected result was the high FD found in old-growth forests, both for the whole category and for most of the single sites as represented in the coenostate space. The highest values of FD and AS were recorded in old-growth sites, even if at larger scales than for high forest: well preserved and relatively undisturbed sites show unique features of high floral heterogeneity (FD) and biocomplexity (spatial dependence through AS).

The statistical tests confirmed the most unequivocal difference between the categories, which is in the characteristic areas of maximum FD: the areas were significantly higher for coppice and old-growth than for high forest. Since most studies only focus on one or two scales^{20,34,47} or don't treat scaling explicitly, this difference might have otherwise been overlooked.

The coppice category provided results which suggest high within-site habitat heterogeneity, a potential value of this management practice for maintaining plant biodiversity: the high characteristic areas, significantly higher than for high forest, and the moderately high AS measures are similar to the

features found in old-growth forest, but FD was consistently lower than for the other two categories. This suggests a mechanism acting at relatively large scales ($\sim 1 \text{ m}^2$) which strongly constrains the freedom of species combinations, possibly a residual effect of logging.

That said, the coppice category is the most varied of the three considered, which is evident by looking at the dispersion in the box plots 9-14 and in the coenostate space 7, and the effect this has on the averaged values for each scale. Dramatic changes happen during the first few decades after management, and this is reflected in the β diversity measures considered.

In general, relative AS showed the same trends as AS, but the differences between categories became smaller, meaning that FD has a not negligible effect on the results obtained by the AS calculations.

The application of the CSR and RS null models to the field data through randomization provided meaningful insights on the mechanisms behind the observed patterns. The consistent results for both FD and AS in all three categories show a significant deviation from the CSR model but not from the RS model, suggesting a non-random, patchy community composition in which intraspecific spatial dependence is important, perhaps because of limited dispersal, polychormonic habits or habitat filtering.

Figure 16 also explains the negative peaks of AS_{eff} in figure 6, since the latter is just the difference between the "field" and "CSR" curves: CSR associatum peaks at lower scales than field AS, when this last one is still low; the rather high values reached by AS in the CSR null model are unexpected, but a positive peak at lower scales than for the field data has been already reported in similar studies⁴⁸. The small deviation between field and RS associatum also explains the not meaningful results obtained when attempting to calculate AS_{eff} from the RS model.

The results of the LAI comparisons showed significant differences between coppice and old-growth, and overall lower values for old-growth than

for the other two categories; comparing the CV_{LAI} % showed lower variation in high forest than in the other two categories. Old-growth sites feature a less dense canopy with high heterogeneity, a combination not shared with other categories, even if the CV_{LAI} % of coppice is likewise high. There's considerable dispersion of LAI values for high forest, so it's possible that some of the older sites in this category have begun the self-thinning process observable in old-growth.

V. Conclusions

The evaluation of close-to-nature management practices and the effectiveness of protection strategies is an open question, especially considering the various aspects of biodiversity and the even more varied models and indices that can be used to analyze and summarize them. This study has shown the potential of using models of the JNP framework to focus on aspects of supra-individual diversity in forest understory, such as the diversity of species combinations and the spatial dependence of populations across different scales.

The results showed differences between the three categories of coppice, high forest and old-growth in at least some of the comparisons, and in particular between high forest and the other two. This shows that many decades are necessary for the effects of protection strategies to become apparent, at least on understory community composition. Old-growth sites stand out for the high maximum values of FD and AS both, high characteristic areas and less dense canopy; regardless of the high variability within this category, the diversity of species combination and the spatial dependence, measured by FD and AS respectively, are useful indices to detect well preserved sites.

Coppice management shows promising characteristics when compared to the other two less recently disturbed categories, with high characteristic areas for both functions and values of AS that aren't significantly lower than for the other categories, suggesting a heterogeneous, organized understory

environment³⁵; the low values of FD and the significant differences in LAI can't nevertheless be ignored, and confirm the importance of preserving and restoring old-growth forests, for the effects observed also through the models.

Despite the considerable variability within each category outlined in different analyses, it was still possible to identify significant differences and draw conclusions from them. With information about stand age, overstory structure and environmental variables, the sensitivity could further be improved through a more rigorous classification, possibly showing the diversity trends of JNP models as a function of age since the last intervention.

Regardless of the results, all the functions analyzed showed maximum values at sampling unit areas between 0.04 m² and 4.25 m², making the chosen sampling scale and extent both necessary and sufficient. This range of areas has been shown to be optimal for the study and monitoring of forest understory, and should be considered in future studies, regardless of the applied models.

VI. Acknowledgments

My thanks go to G.Campetella and S.Chelli for their continuous assistance, Z.Zhengxue for coding troubleshooting; to all the above, plus R.Canullo, M.Cervellini, J.L.Tsakalos, R.Pennesi and V.Cesaroni for the field work.

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